

Homophobia, economic precarity and the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people in a 153-country survey

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Abstract

We explored the well-being of sexual and gender diverse (LGBTQ+) people using three socioecological dimensions of homophobia, family, community and national, and their socioeconomic status via a convenience sample of 82,324 participants. Participants from the Middle East and North Africa reported the lowest subjective well-being ($M=4.78$, $SD=2.70$), followed by Eastern Europe and Central Asia ($M=5.22$, $SD=2.13$). Structural Homophobic Climate Index was negatively related to LGBTQ+ well-being the most ($\beta=-1.68$, 95%CI [-2.38, -0.99]), followed by family-level homophobia ($\beta=-0.84$, 95%CI [-0.87, -0.81]). Economic precarity significantly interacted with the negative association between homophobia and participants' well-being. The weight of a country's homophobic climate on well-being was nearly halved for economically secure participants compared to those economically deprived. Participants unaware of their HIV status reported the lowest well-being ($\beta=-0.20$, 95%CI [-0.23 to -0.16]) controlling for homophobia. Public health measures should address homophobic stigma and discrimination, focusing on the lowest socioeconomic strata.

Keywords: Discrimination, Happiness, HIV/AIDS, Homophobia, LGBT, Poverty, Stigma, Well-being

Introduction

Well-being has long been associated with income and standard of living. The concept has evolved over recent decades to include subjective and ecological components(1, 2) as well as other non-monetary quality-of-life dimensions(3). Subjective components encompass life satisfaction, the presence of positive emotions, and the absence of negative ones(4). In other words, subjective well-being refers to how individuals feel or think their life is going. This evaluation of one's life is generally based on factors that one considers relevant(5), and it varies between countries(6) and cultures(2, 7), and by vulnerability(8) and individual characteristics(9, 10). Although limited, empirical evidence on the determinants of happiness among individuals who identify as lesbian, gay men, bisexual, transgender or questioning, as well as other sexual and gender diverse (LGBTQ+) people(11-13), tends to confirm the presence of determinants similar to those found in the general population (14, 15). However, specific determinants also play a pivotal role, such as family support(16, 17), community support(18, 19), and relationships with stigma and discrimination based on sexual and gender characteristics, also known as homophobia(20-23) and queerphobia(24-27).

We use 'homophobia' as an umbrella term for all forms of stigma and discrimination based on sexual and gender characteristics faced by all sexual and gender diverse individuals. Homophobia is associated with the denial, denigration and stigmatisation of any non-heterosexual behaviour, identity, relationship or community(28). Changes in contemporary societies suggest considering homophobia as a complex system(29), closely imbricated with hetero-normativity, which focuses on the structures and beliefs that enshrine heterosexual relationships as the norm(30). As such, we posit that the use of a socioecological approach(2, 31) to homophobia will enable us to analyse complex interactions between the different dimensions of heterosexist stigma and discrimination and well-being among sexual and gender diverse people. Such an approach has been increasingly used in public health studies of minorities(32-34). It considers the role of various environmental systems of daily life, such as public space, workplaces, healthcare facilities, community, family and intrapersonal determinants.

Homophobia is widespread in most countries(35) and is negatively correlated with the health and well-being of sexual and gender diverse people(33, 36-40). More than one third of nations have laws that criminalise same-sex relationships between consenting adults(41). Beyond an aggregate assessment of stigma and discrimination at the country (macro) level, a socioecological approach allows for the assessment of how heteronormativity translates in the everyday lives of sexual and gender minorities. We applied a three-level assessment of homophobia –family, local, and national– guided by the *micro-meso-macro* approach frequently used in sociology and economics(42-45) and applied to capture discrimination at different levels of society(46-48) and well-being in high-income countries(49-51). One advantage of this approach, especially with the introduction of a meso level, is the possibility of studying the potential intersections between stigma and discrimination and other factors(52-55) and, in a second step, the correlation between the above intersections and the well-being of LGBTQ+ individuals, such as socioeconomic status, social support or health. In this study, we focused on economic precarity.

Prior studies have shown an association between the various socioecological dimensions of stigma and discrimination related to sexual and gender diversity and economic precarity among LGBTQ+ people at both the individual(56-59) and macroeconomic levels(60, 61). Precarity relates to the inequality faced by LGBTQ+ individuals in terms of insecurity, vulnerability and destabilisation(62). By extension, economic precarity focuses on financial and economic instability, food insecurity and access to reliable housing and healthcare(63). The financial and economic precarity faced by LGBTQ+ individuals has been associated with greater stress, anxiety and depression, which may be linked to their well-being(64, 65). Public health and social epidemiology research also highlights the role of a socioeconomic gradient in health(66), particularly mental health(67). However, a significant gap appears to exist in understanding how economic precarity observed at the micro-level interacts with

the various dimensions of homophobia and how this interaction correlates with well-being among sexual and gender diverse people outside high-income countries(68).

Studies from high-income countries suggest that the subjective well-being of sexual and gender diverse individuals tends to be lower than that of the general population(69-71). However, little is known about the other regions of the globe. Key determinants of happiness, such as supportive social relationships (including family), are positively associated with life satisfaction among both LGBTQ+ people and the general population(5, 72), whereas stigma and discrimination related to sexual and gender diversity are negatively associated with life satisfaction(73, 74). Research has shown a positive association between happiness and economic security among the general population(5, 6, 75), but a lack of evidence remains regarding this association among LGBTQ+ individuals. This study aimed to examine how the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people is associated with three ecological dimensions of homophobia (family, local community, and national) and the intersecting association with economic security. In line with the socioecological perspective, we hypothesised that higher economic security (lower economic precarity) may moderate the strength of the negative association between homophobic discrimination and well-being in LGBTQ+ communities.

We used primary data from the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey, which gathered responses from more than 115,000 sexual and gender diverse participants from 200 countries and territories. Participants were recruited through a mix of convenience sample methods, combining online recruitment on social networks and social media platforms with snowball sampling, using either community-based networks in settings where the internet penetration rate was low or online private groups in settings where LGBTQ+ social media were not authorised and personal safety was a concern. Subjective well-being was measured using the Cantril ladder(76). The various dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination were measured with questions on family support, homophobic reactions(77, 78), and the Homophobic Climate Index (HCI)(34). We developed a linear multilevel mixed-effect model and used interactions to study the possible mitigating role of economic status on the relationship between homophobia and subjective well-being. We completed the analysis with an assessment of the weight or importance of each dimension of homophobic stigma and discrimination on LGBTQ+ well-being. All econometric models used the same sample and control variables described in Table 1. A complete description of the variables and methods is presented in the Methods section.

Results

This section is divided into two parts. First, descriptive results from the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey are presented, followed by the results of inferential statistics assessing the study's hypothesis.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the main characteristics of the study population recruited through convenience sample methods (n=82,324). Almost three quarters of participants identified as gay men (72.4%), and nearly one fifth (18.1%) identified as bisexual. Lesbians and other sexual diverse participants represented 8.7% of the participants. Most participants identified as cisgender (87.2%), men (80.5%) or women (6.7%). One out of eight participants (12.8%) identified as non-binary or transgender. The regional repartition of participants per sexual and gender identity is presented in Supplementary Material (SM) S1.

Approximately one third of participants (31.2%) were aged 18–24 years, and more than one third (37.2%) were aged over 35 years. The detailed representation of participants per sexual and gender identity and age is presented in Supplementary Material S1. Most participants were single (63.1%), and more than two thirds had a university degree (71.6%). The majority were employed (69.1%), either full- or part-time, whereas one tenth (10.5%) were unemployed.

Almost two thirds of the participants self-reported HIV-negative status (63%), more than one in ten (11%) reported living with HIV and nearly one quarter (22.6%) reported not knowing their HIV serostatus. More than one third of participants (39.5%) reported that their present income was sufficient to cover their monthly expenses, and more than one quarter (26.2%) considered themselves to be in economic precarity (having difficulty living with their current income).

Regarding subjective well-being among LGBTQ+ participants, measured with the happiness index, one quarter (25%) reported suffering, 32% indicated they were struggling, and 43% were thriving. Fig. 1 shows the heterogeneity in the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ communities worldwide. Sexual and gender diverse communities in Latin America reported the highest share of participants thriving in life (52%). Conversely, LGBTQ+ participants living in the Middle East and North Africa reported both the lowest share of LGBTQ+ individuals thriving (26%) and the highest share of LGBTQ+ individuals suffering in life (44%). Those in Eastern Europe and Central Asia reported the second-highest share of LGBTQ+ people suffering in life (35%). An analysis of variance confirms that these regional differences are statistically significant ($F(5, 82, 318) = 575.12, p < .001$), with an effect size of $\eta^2 = 0.034$, indicating that 3.4% of the variance in well-being is explained by region. See SM S2.

Fig. 1 | Distribution of the LGBTQ+ Happiness Index Worldwide.

Comparisons of the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ participants with that of the general population from the World Happiness Report(79) should be cautious. The Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey used convenience samples that do not necessarily represent sexual and gender diverse people at the country level. We examined whether the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ participants differed from that of the general population in the same countries, using two-tailed independent t-tests. LGBTQ+ participants from Western Europe and North America reported lower life satisfaction compared to the general population ($6.1 < 6.6, t(38) = 4.92, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.3, 0.7]$). Conversely, LGBTQ+ individuals reported higher life satisfaction in Asia and the Pacific ($6.1 > 5.4, t(20) = -3.10, p = .0028, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.1 \text{ to } -0.3]$) and Sub-Saharan Africa ($5.87 > 4.3, t(29) = -8.95, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.8 \text{ to } -1.2]$). We examine these findings in the Discussion Section. See SM S3 for detailed tables by country and region.

Regarding homophobic stigma and discrimination (Fig. 2), 21% of participants worldwide reported that they had been physically assaulted because someone knew or presumed their sexual orientation or gender identity. Sub-Saharan Africa was the region with the highest proportion of participants reporting homophobic reactions: 36% reported physical violence because someone knew or presumed their sexual orientation or gender identity. Conversely, the lowest proportions of homophobic reactions were reported in Asia and the Pacific. Furthermore, 47% of participants felt that their families did not accept them. The Middle East and North Africa were the regions where LGBTQ+ individuals reported the highest proportion of non-acceptance from their families (74%). Across the 153 countries included in the study, the HCI ($M = 0.58, SD = 0.14$) had a skewed distribution, with 57 countries (37%) below the mean (a less homophobic climate), and 96 countries (63%) above the mean.

Fig. 2 | Distribution of individual-level homophobic measures worldwide.

Inferential statistics

The association between well-being and homophobia

Table 1 shows the results of the multilevel model. Beta coefficients (β) indicate the effect sizes. Being non-binary ($\beta = -0.18, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.24 \text{ to } -0.12]$) or a cisgender woman ($\beta = -0.26, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.33 \text{ to } -0.19]$) was negatively associated with happiness, compared with being a cisgender man. The negative coefficient for age ($\beta = -0.07, p = .018, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.12 \text{ to } -0.01]$) indicates that happiness decreased as age increased, and the positive coefficient for age squared ($\beta = 0.03, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.02 \text{ to } 0.04]$) suggests that the rate of decline in happiness slowed and eventually reversed. This combination corresponded to a U-shaped relationship between age and subjective well-being among LGBTQ+ people, consistent with the literature(80-83).

Compared to those who reported being HIV-negative, LGBTQ+ participants living with HIV reported a reduction of 0.14 points ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.18 \text{ to } -0.09]$) in their subjective well-being. Being unaware of one's HIV status was associated with a 0.20-point reduction ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.23 \text{ to } -0.16]$) in their life satisfaction scale. Finally, LGBTQ+ participants who chose not to disclose their HIV status reported slightly higher levels of happiness ($\beta = 0.08, p = .030, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.01, 0.14]$).

All four socioecological measures of homophobic stigma and discrimination were associated with lower subjective well-being scores. The family level ($\beta = -0.84, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.87 \text{ to } -0.81]$), the community level, with verbal homophobic insults ($\beta = -0.24, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.27 \text{ to } -0.21]$) and physical homophobic assaults ($\beta = -0.21, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.25 \text{ to } -0.18]$), and the structural level measured by the HCI ($\beta = -1.68, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-2.38 \text{ to } -0.99]$) were all associated with lower LGBTQ+ well-being.

Table 1 | Descriptive statistics and multilevel regression model of the association between well-being and socioeconomic, health, and homophobia-related variables.

Fig.3 shows the strength of the association between the three socioecological dimensions of homophobia and well-being by sexual identity (Fig. 3a) and region (Fig. 3b). The detailed regression results can be found in SMS4. The three dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination were negatively associated with well-being across all sexual identities and most regions with one exception in Eastern Europe and Central Asia where the association between HCI and well-being was positive ($\beta = 2.22, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.40, 4.04], p = .017$). Among sexual identities, this negative association was more pronounced in the first two dimensions of homophobia among queer and gay men. For queer individuals, we observed negative associations between well-being and family homophobia ($\beta = -1.07, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.24 \text{ to } -0.91], p < .001$) as well as homophobic reactions, both verbal ($\beta = -0.45, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.63 \text{ to } -0.27], p < .001$) and physical ($\beta = -0.31, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.51 \text{ to } -0.10], p = .004$) ones. Gay men reported negative associations between their well-being and family homophobia ($\beta = -0.82, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.85 \text{ to } -0.78], p < .001$), and verbal ($\beta = -0.25, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.29 \text{ to } -0.22], p < .001$) or physical ($\beta = -0.21, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.25 \text{ to } -0.17], p < .001$) homophobic reactions. Regarding the third dimension of homophobia, lesbian individuals ($\beta = -1.91, 95\% \text{ CI } [-3.23 \text{ to } -0.58], p = .005$) and gay men ($\beta = -1.90, 95\% \text{ CI } [-2.64 \text{ to } -1.16], p < .001$) reported negative associations between their well-being and the country's homophobic climate, followed by queer individuals ($\beta = -1.67, 95\% \text{ CI } [-3.12 \text{ to } -0.22], p = .024$).

LGBTQ+ participants from the Middle East and North Africa region exhibited strong negative association between well-being and the three dimensions of homophobia and happiness: Family homophobia ($\beta = -1.38, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.58 \text{ to } -1.17], p < .001$), homophobic insult ($\beta = -0.31, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.52 \text{ to } -0.11], p = .002$), and homophobic physical reactions ($\beta = -0.28, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.46 \text{ to } -0.10], p < .001$). At the structural level, the homophobic climate in countries of this region has negative association across all regions ($\beta = -3.53, 95\% \text{ CI } [-6.05 \text{ to } -1.00], p = .006$). Participants from sub-Saharan Africa also reported a high negative association between their well-being and homophobia, particularly at the community

level with verbal ($\beta = -0.51, 95\% [-0.70 \text{ to } -0.32], p < .001$), and physical ($\beta = -0.28, 95\% [-0.46 \text{ to } -0.10], p = .003$) homophobic reactions.

Fig. 3 | Homophobia and well-being: strength of the association by sexual identity and by region.

The mitigating role of individuals' economic situation

Table 2 summarises the results of the multilevel models for the three dimensions of homophobia according to the socioeconomic situation of the study population. The associations between the three socioecological dimensions of homophobia and happiness remained negative and statistically significant for all income groups. When we compared the coefficients across each group, we observed that the magnitude of the HCI had an inverse relationship with the precarity level of LGBTQ+ participants, ranging from -2.29 ($95\% \text{ CI } [-3.26 \text{ to } -1.33], p < .001$) for those having difficulty living on their present income to -1.17 ($95\% \text{ CI } [-1.88 \text{ to } -0.47], p = .001$) for those living comfortably on their present income. In other words, the better the economic and financial security of participants, the less their subjective well-being appears to be associated with the homophobic climate of their country. This progression along the economic gradient was also reported by participants encountering homophobia from their families and those experiencing physical homophobic reactions. See SMS 5 for the complete regressions.

Table 2 | The Association Between Well-being and the Three Dimensions of Homophobia, Clustered by Income Level.

Multilevel model with interactions

Table 3 shows the correlations between the three dimensions of homophobia and the happiness of sexual and gender diverse individuals, incorporating interactions to test whether these relationships varied by income level (reference group: participants having difficulty living on their present income). Most interactions were statistically significant, with one exception: there was no statistically significant difference between homophobic verbal reactions and the level of happiness of the wealthiest group ($\Delta\beta = -0.03, p = .49, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.11, 0.05]$). The interactions are positive for participants living comfortably than for those merely covering monthly expenses on their present income. For example, the interaction coefficient for family homophobia were $\Delta\beta = 0.12$ ($p = .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.05, 0.20]$) and $\Delta\beta = 0.15$ ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.08, 0.22]$), respectively. For the country-level homophobic climate, they were $\Delta\beta = 0.49$ ($p = .02, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.08, 0.97]$) and $\Delta\beta = 1.06$ ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.64, 1.47]$). These interactions indicate a buffering or mitigating association of economic and financial stability in the relationship between homophobia and the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ people.

One can illustrate this buffering association of economic security from Table 3: The main effect for physical homophobic reaction is $\beta = -0.322$ ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.384 \text{ to } -0.260]$) in the reference group. The interaction coefficients are $\Delta\beta = +0.15$ ($p = .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.06, 0.23]$) for participants merely covering monthly expenses and $\Delta\beta = +0.20$ ($p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.11, 0.29]$) for those living comfortably on their present income. Adding the interaction terms yields estimated slopes of $\beta = -0.17$ ($= -0.32 + 0.15$) and $\beta = -0.12$ ($= -0.32 + 0.20$), respectively, showing a progressive attenuation of the negative association as economic security increases. The consistency of this result with earlier analyses (Table 2) is further developed in the Discussion.

Table 3 | Association between well-being and the three dimensions of homophobia, including interactions with economic security.

Analysis per level of country inequality

We investigated whether country-level inequality, measured with the Gini coefficient, moderated the association between the three socioecological dimensions of homophobia and well-being. Detailed regression results can be found in SM S6. In both lower- and higher-inequality country strata, higher family homophobia, verbal and physical homophobic reactions were associated with lower well-being.

We observed a prevalent negative correlation between physical homophobic reactions and the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ individuals living in economic precarity across all inequality contexts. The association was similar across inequality levels: $\beta = -.27$ (95% CI [-0.37 to -0.16], $p < .001$) in lower-inequality countries and $\beta = -.28$ (95% CI [-0.39 to -0.16], $p < .001$) in higher-inequality countries (see SM S6, Table S6.7). A direct lower- vs higher-inequality contrast of the slopes from the interaction model showed no statistically significant difference ($\Delta\beta = -0.01$, $p = .892$, 95% CI [-0.17, 0.15]). See SM S6, Table S6.8. In other words, we found no evidence that the relationship between physical homophobic reaction and well-being differed by country inequality.

For countries' homophobic climates, some point estimates differed numerically across the levels of inequality and participants' economic security, but the cross-inequality interaction showed no statistically significant difference ($\Delta\beta = 0.20$, $p = .726$, 95% CI [-0.89, 1.28]).

Dominance analysis

Dominance analysis(84) complements the regression analysis by providing information on the relative importance(85) of the two predictors of interest in this study, (i) the socioecological dimensions of homophobia and (ii) economic precarity, on the happiness of sexual and gender diverse people. This approach highlights how the relative importance (expressed in % points) of each dimension of homophobia varied across the levels of economic precarity, providing a more precise quantification of the central hypothesis, informing that the association between homophobia and well-being may differ depending on an individual's economic situation. Table 4 presents the standardised dominance statistics for the three socioecological dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination across the gradient of economic precarity. The cumulative variation in well-being explained by the three homophobic dimensions was greater for deprived individuals (36.5%) compared to those living comfortably on their present income (13.3%). The family dimension dominated the other dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination across all economic profiles, explaining, on average, 12.4% [95% CI (10.5, 14.3)] of the level of happiness of LGBTQ+ participants around the world; it represents 47.5% of the cumulative average variation in subjective well-being explained by homophobia. The dominance statistics of the community dimension of homophobia on well-being among LGBTQ+ individuals, as measured by homophobic reactions faced by LGBTQ+ populations, were greater among those living in economic precarity, representing 1.66 and 3.5 times(86) that of those covering monthly expenses with their present income and those living comfortably on their present income, respectively(86). The country dimension of homophobia, measured using the country's homophobic climate, accounted for 10.6% of the level of happiness of those who were having difficulty living on their present income (29% of the cumulative explained variation in well-being, for all dimensions of homophobia among this group). This is 3.93 times that of those living in secure economic conditions.

Table 4 | Relative importance of the three dimensions of homophobia on well-being, clustered by level of economic security.

Sensitivity analysis

We performed a sensitivity analysis to assess the robustness of our findings using various transformations to assess the cardinality of the subjective well-being measure of the Cantril ladder of life satisfaction. We first applied monotonic transformations to life satisfaction's 11 rungs to determine whether these transformations would alter the coefficients of our key variables(87, 88). We then transformed the outcome variable using the dichotomous around the median test(89), which splits the happiness variable around its median to create two dichotomous variables for comparative analysis. See SMS7. Both sensitivity analyses confirmed that the three dimensions of homophobia were negatively associated with the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people.

Discussion

This study explored the relationship between well-being and various dimensions of homophobia using a socioecological, multilevel model and the mitigating role of socioeconomic status in this relationship.

Family, community and country socioecological dimensions of homophobia were strongly negatively associated with the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people. Additionally, our study identifies the interactions and compounding association of the three dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination worldwide, providing insights into an under-researched reality.

The opening result provides a global picture of LGBTQ+ people's well-being, including in regions previously understudied, contributing to current knowledge of the factors associated with their well-being(90-92). The lowest rate of LGBTQ+ people's well-being was observed in the Middle East and North Africa, and the Eastern Europe and Central Asia regions. These findings support evidence-based advocacy efforts at the national level to address criminalising legislation and homophobic attitudes toward sexual and gender diverse communities.

Our findings, based on a convenient non-probabilistic sample, are consistent with existing literature reporting that the subjective well-being of sexual and gender diverse individuals was lower than that of the general population in Western countries(69-71). They suggest a nuanced picture across regions, with LGBTQ+ participants from Asia and the Pacific and Sub-Saharan Africa reporting greater subjective well-being compared to the general population. These findings should be interpreted cautiously as they do not necessarily represent countries' LGBTQ+ populations. However, they open the floor to interesting questions about regional variations in subjective well-being and their possible association with the local context, social support, and cultural differences that should be further investigated with representative samples.

We showed the predominant relationship between family support, or lack thereof, and the subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ individuals. This association remained consistently high in both lower- and higher-inequality settings. It emphasises the importance of including the family dimension of homophobia, where sexuality and sexual orientation can be particularly controlled(93-95). Family relationships can deteriorate when homosexuality is disclosed, resulting in denial, mockery, insult, harassment, and rejection, which have been associated with mental and physical health degradation(96). Our findings confirm the negative association between family homophobia and the well-being of sexual and gender diverse people beyond the Western world(50, 51) and China(97). Our findings also support the literature addressing the challenge of family acceptance in the Global South, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and the Middle East and North Africa regions, where family is a significant element of societal constructs that value fertility, lineage and kinship(98). Moreover, family homophobia may be influenced by family codes, colonial heritage, and religious laws(99-103). Our

findings suggest a need for more research on the existing and emerging family values and stressors that can perpetuate the concealment of sexual or gender identity and lower well-being.

Economic precarity significantly interacted with the negative association between homophobic reactions and well-being. The dominance analysis showed that the weight of a country's homophobic climate on well-being was nearly halved for LGBTQ+ participants living comfortably on their present income compared to those who were economically deprived. However, this mitigating role of the social gradient did not vary significantly between higher- or lower-inequality settings, suggesting that the protective effect of economic security operates consistently across diverse national contexts. These findings contribute to the literature on how income, well-being, health and 'existential' equalities(104) are distributed across societies(105), suggesting that stigma and discrimination based on sexual and gender diversity transcend income inequality. For LGBTQ+ individuals facing economic precarity, welfare generosity(106), safety nets and other redistributive mechanisms may not be sufficient to counterbalance the loss in well-being associated with country's homophobic climate. This conclusion aligns with studies from high-income countries(106, 107) and confirms that the pattern is global, including in low- and middle-income countries.

The situation of LGBTQ+ participants living comfortably on their present income suggests that, unlike those in economic precarity, they may be able to better access health services, supportive social network services, secure neighbourhoods and other measures to mitigate the adverse effects of institutional homophobia, particularly in more unequal societies. If the literature extensively corroborates the association between income and greater life satisfaction in the general population(108-111), we found limited evidence(112, 113), primarily from Western countries, supporting the moderating role of income on the relationship between homophobia and the well-being of LGBTQ+ populations. These findings suggest that economic development and social benefits aimed at reducing inequality may have only a limited impact on LGBTQ+ people's well-being if structural homophobia is not addressed.

The differentiated strength of association per economic gradient highlights the relationship between homophobic physical assault and one's presumed sexual orientation or gender identity. The subjective well-being of the poorest LGBTQ+ individuals was strongly negatively correlated with homophobic reactions. These results extend previous findings from Europe and North America(52, 114, 115) to low- and middle-income countries. Further research could inform the means available to the wealthier category and how these could be brought to individuals living in economic precarity. Recent systematic reviews have argued that non-heterosexual identity tends to be a determinant factor in one's difficulties in accessing health care(116, 117), which may increase the vulnerability of sexual and gender diverse people, especially those in economic precarity. The findings also highlight the role of LGBTQ+-inclusive community-based healthcare initiatives in bridging the gap in specialised, culturally competent and affirmative mental health needs(19, 117-119).

HIV status was highly correlated with the subjective well-being of sexual and gender diverse people, after controlling for homophobia. Participants living with HIV reported a small reduction in their well-being compared to those who were HIV-negative. This may reflect the impact of antiretroviral therapy and undetectable HIV viral load on the life expectancy of people living with HIV, being similar to that of HIV-negative individuals(120). This finding aligns with several studies reporting the positive effect of coping strategies(121, 122) with a gain in well-being and happiness among people living with HIV(123). Participants unaware of their HIV status reported the lowest level of well-being after controlling for homophobia. This finding has implications for HIV testing initiatives among LGBTQ+ populations, suggesting the need to consider subjective well-being and mental health as potential determinants of HIV testing intentions.

Our study has several limitations, starting with representativeness. In many countries, sexual and gender diverse people are stigmatised and even criminalised, which makes reaching out to

representative samples difficult. This work was based on an online survey that recruited participants through social networks and community-based organisations. It applied a non-probabilistic convenience sampling method that is appropriate for marginalised, hard-to-reach population groups(124-127). It is, nevertheless, more subject to selection biases compared to probabilistic samples(128). Per their construct, results from non-probabilistic convenience sampling methods are not meant to be representative at a country level, and caution should be exercised when generalising our findings. Additionally, the rate of missingness for specific questions, such as the self-declared HIV status, must be acknowledged. We investigated the possible biases that these skipped questions could have on our findings. These not-at-random skipped questions were corroborated by other studies(129-131) and did not affect the findings. This should not imply that skipped answers on HIV status should be ignored; a non-response is a response and should be investigated in future studies. Nevertheless, a growing body of evidence supports the use of online convenience sampling methods(132-134), particularly among sexual and gender diverse communities(135), who are significantly more active on the internet and social media than the general population(136-140). For the last decade, the ability to use social media for epidemiological and HIV prevention, treatment and care needs among gay men and transgender individuals has continued to improve, particularly in low- and middle-income countries(141). Ultimately, online convenience sampling using social networks offers the possibility to reach sexual and gender diverse individuals across a broad range of countries and settings, including some with no reported estimates of LGBTQ+ people(127). Ultimately, recognising and including sexual and gender diverse people should translate into their inclusion in national and international representative statistics and censuses.

The participation rate varied between regions, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and the Middle East and North Africa regions. Contextual factors such as legal(35), religious and pervasive stigma and discrimination against LGBTQ+(142) may have affected participation in these settings. Additionally, external factors such as lower internet penetration, costly data usage(142) and the limited presence of social networks on the African continent made it harder for sexual and gender diverse individuals to participate in the survey. However, recent studies show the resilience and willingness of LGBTQ+ individuals from the Middle East and North Africa to fight for their rights and recognition(143-146). The internet and social media are generally perceived as secure spaces to be who they want, and for social support(146) and advocacy(147, 148). In these regions, more than in others, the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey used proportionately more informal community-based organisations and private networks or groups on popular social media. These private networks were built by and for sexual and gender diverse communities. This highlights the need for more research and datasets in African and Middle Eastern regions to triangulate with and assess whether contextual and external factors impact the response rates in these regions.

Biases relate to the surveyed population groups(128, 149), such as younger age, living in cities, higher education, and potentially engaging in certain behaviours that carry higher HIV risk(150). Additionally, digital divide and social media engagement vary by country, potentially affecting participation in and representativeness of online surveys(151, 152). It is difficult to predict or control the extent and direction of internet convenience sampling selection bias under- or overestimating the relationships between sample characteristics and measured outcomes(153, 154). Regarding the first type of bias, participants' age, education, gender and sexual identity were skewed toward younger, cisgender gay men, and tertiary education. These characteristics, although skewed, do not contradict the findings of similar studies in the United States, indicating that gay men tend to have higher educational achievement compared to heterosexual and other sexual and gender diverse people(155-157). We identified and included demographic covariates associated with the potential bias, together with appropriate variable adjustments(10, 110, 158, 159) to reduce, but not eliminate, the potential bias(160, 161). We also conducted external validity checks with available and comparable data from existing convenience sampling online surveys in Europe(157, 162) and Latin America(163, 164). Regarding the second type of bias, the survey team partnered with civil society and community-based organisations, as well as development partners who provided computer-assisted personal interviews or a 'safe-haven room' where LGBTQ+ members could participate in the survey.

Another limitation relates to the fact that the survey questionnaire was self-administered. It is therefore impossible to assess the accuracy of self-reported data on HIV status, subjective well-being and homophobic reactions. Nevertheless, it is reasonable to assume that participants had little motive to misrepresent their perceived situation, given that the participation in the study was voluntary, anonymous and uncompensated. Moreover, participants in online surveys generally report lower desirability bias than other sampling methods(165-167).

Our results identified the magnitude, for sexual and gender diverse people, of a feature constant in societies: the social gradient in the suffering of ill-treatment. The archetypal case is social inequities in diseases such as HIV, a quasi-universal and permanent feature of public health disparities driven by social determinants(66). The socioecological approach to homophobia has highlighted an economic inequality dimension resulting from stigma and discrimination based on sexual and gender diversity. Policymakers should prioritise policies to eliminate homophobia and promote LGBTQ+ rights with a particular focus on the lowest socioeconomic strata.

Methods

Ethics approval and consent to participate:

The data used in this study were collected following all relevant ethical regulations. The survey methods followed the guidelines and principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER). The online questionnaire was assessed and tested to ensure that it entailed minimal risk regarding potential stress or anxiety while responding. The questionnaire compiled questions previously used in other surveys and, to the best of our knowledge, did not present any physical risk.

The Global LGBT Happiness Study research protocol was approved by the Research Board of Ethics of Aix-Marseille University (No.2019-14-03-004) and by the Research Ethics Review Committee of the World Health Organization (No.ERC.0003175).

Participants had to provide their informed consent to access the survey. Participants below 18 years old or who did not provide a numerical value for their age were not included in the study. Participation in the survey was voluntary, and no monetary incentive was given to complete the questionnaire. Participants could skip questions that they did not feel comfortable with or did not want to answer. Participants could interrupt the survey at any moment with an exit button on every questionnaire page, and their data were automatically and permanently deleted. No trackers, identifiers or geolocation data were collected from participants.

Data

No statistical methods were used to pre-determine sample sizes. An *a priori* sample size was set at 100 participants per country, except for microstates, based on comparable surveys, such as the EMIS and LAMIS, and pragmatic considerations of time and cost of data collection. Our sample sizes are larger than those reported in previous publications(77, 78, 163, 168).

Individual data were obtained from the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey conducted from 1 May 2019 to 31 December 2019. Participation consisted of answering a 12-minute global online questionnaire on LGBTQ+ people available in 32 languages. The questionnaire was developed using validated instruments and multiple consultations with representatives of LGBTQ+ communities, sociologists, epidemiologists and economists. To ensure its acceptability within the communities, the questionnaire was initially tested among 5,000 participants from 12 countries in various regions.

Participation in the survey was voluntary, and no monetary incentive was given to complete the questionnaire. Participants could skip questions that they did not want to answer and exit the survey at any time. The eligibility criteria were: (i) being over 18 years of age, and (ii) providing informed consent. A total of 115,797 participants from more than 200 countries and territories responded to the questionnaire. This study included participants who answered all the measures of interest described in Table 1. We did not impute any missing data because no other datasets were available to predict missing data points without the risk of misrepresentation. The final sample size of this study is 82,324 sexual and gender diverse participants.

A detailed description of the methods and design of the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness survey is available elsewhere (169). The research protocol, including the complete questionnaire, is available in the Online Supplementary Material. In principle, the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Study aimed to generate large and geographically diverse datasets of the largely ignored sexual and gender minority population. It combined information on the well-being, behavioural sciences, health behaviour, HIV, and socioeconomic vulnerability of LGBTQ+ populations.

Participants were recruited through a combination of online convenience sampling methods involving social media platforms, dating applications, LGBTQ+ private groups on popular social media, with more

than 300 community-based organisations at global and national levels. The CBOs and development partners provided computer-assisted personal interviews or a 'safe-haven room' with a computer connected to the internet where LGBTQ+ members could participate in the survey. This support was indispensable in territories where LGBTQ+ communities faced challenges accessing the internet (e.g. conflict zones, low internet penetration rate or expensive data usage), such as the Central African Republic, Haiti, Mauritania, Mozambique, Liberia and the Pacific Small States. This combination of sampling methods enabled to reach marginalised population groups that would have been missed otherwise. The survey team also involved celebrities, community activists, and influencers who promoted the survey on their websites, networks, and social media accounts. In countries favouring a national internet, such as China, the team partnered with the largest LGBTQ+ social network (Blued, 40 million members), in addition to using an *ad hoc* anonymous and encrypted online survey tool available. LGBTQ+ people in these territories also promoted the survey through Chinese social networks such as WeChat.

The survey benefited from the increasing access to the internet and growing demand among sexual and gender minority individuals for online social networks. The internet has been increasingly used to recruit sexual and gender minority individuals, especially in HIV research(135, 154). The advantages of using this method include faster recruitment, lower operational costs, and a greater level of anonymity provided to participants, which allows researchers to capture more sexual and gender diversity without risking participants' self-disclosure of their sexual orientation, compared with those recruited in person and from venues(153, 170-172). Furthermore, internet sampling typically enables researchers to reach more respondents than any other method. A systematic literature review showed that internet sampling reached a total of 225,320 participants in 33 selected studies, compared to 82,004 participants reached by respondent-driven sampling in 77 studies, and 55,193 participants reached by time-location sampling in 42 studies (126).

Recruiting through social networks may have induced a selection bias, however. We decided not to introduce weighting or statistical methods such as propensity score matching to the sample, because most participants were from countries and regions not surveyed before; therefore, margins would be unknown if any reweighting was intended. Additionally, to check the validity of our sample, we compared some results from another survey, the European MSM Internet Survey(77), with a similar subset of individuals to our dataset. Student tests confirmed similarity in the profiles of the responses. The sample in the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey was younger, lower economic security and reported slightly higher incidences of anxiety and depression (see SMS8 for more details). More comparisons with low- and middle-income countries would be suitable, but this was impossible given the scarcity of data in these settings.

Country-level data were obtained from the World Bank(173), UNDP Human Development Reports(174) and UNAIDS(175). They included a set of macroeconomic indicators characterising each country's social, political, economic and epidemiological context, including homophobia.

Study population

The study population for this research comprised participants for whom the following information was available: (i) sex at birth, (ii) sexual orientation, and (iii) gender identity (n=82,324 participants in 153 countries). See SMS1 for more details on the distribution of the study population across regions, sexual and gender identity and age.

Dependent variable

Defining well-being and life satisfaction has always been challenging, which may be why social scientists and economists have focused more on measuring its subjective or objective dimensions than on its definition(4-6). The study of well-being has gained much traction in the last two decades(7), with a wealth of literature published on the objective and subjective determinants of life satisfaction, which is well summarised by Voukelatou(8). Consequently, economists increasingly use measures of happiness or subjective well-being in surveys(176-179). We used the Cantril ladder(76) of life satisfaction to measure subjective well-being; this validated instrument is also widely used in surveys

among the general population(6). The question posed to the participants was: 'Imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top, representing happiness in your life. On which step of the ladder do you stand at this time? Answer 0 corresponds to the worst possible life for you and answer 10 to the best possible life.' The 11-item variable was treated as a linear variable(180).

The subjective well-being of LGBTQ+ participants was assembled from individual scores from each region following established thresholds(181):

- Suffering: The participant's well-being is at high risk. Includes happiness values from 0 to 4.
- Struggling: The participant's well-being is moderate. Includes happiness values of 5 and 6.
- Thriving: The participant's well-being is strong. Includes happiness values from 7 to 10.

A Welch's ANOVA pairwise comparison indicated that LGBTQ+ people's life satisfaction varied across Eastern Europe and Central Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and the Middle East and North Africa regions. There was no statistically significant difference between the sub-Saharan Africa and Asia and the Pacific ($p=0.106$, 95% CI [-0.095 to 0.009]), and Western and Central Europe and North America ($p=0.990$, 95% CI [-0.078 to 0.077]) regions. See SM S2.

Independent variables

We used a socioecological approach to consider three dimensions of homophobic stigma and discrimination: (i) the family dimension, (ii) the local community dimension, and (iii) the national dimension. More precisely, the family dimension of homophobic stigma and discrimination was proxied by the perceived homophobia in the family circle, measured with the question: 'Does your family accept you as you are?' using a five-item Likert scale, from *strongly disagree* to *strongly agree*. We created a dichotomised variable by aggregating 'strongly disagree', 'disagree', and 'I don't know' together and 'agree' and 'strongly agree' together. The local community dimension was measured by the reported experience of homophobic reactions: being verbally insulted and physically assaulted because someone knew or presumed one's sexual orientation or gender identity. These validated measures are commonly used in surveys to capture homophobic reactions(77, 78). The national dimension was proxied by the recently developed HCI(34), a measure reflecting institutional and social homophobia. The HCI was designed to be relevant to the whole spectrum of sexual and gender diversity. Institutional homophobia was assessed by the existence or enforcement of 11 laws characterising the level of institutionalised homophobia in a country(35, 182). Social homophobia was measured by two variables on the tolerance and acceptance of same-sex relationships in the general population, collected through representative surveys conducted worldwide(183, 184).

Economic precarity was measured through participants' self-assessment of their current income using a five-item Likert scale. Participants were asked: 'Which comes closest to your feelings about your income these days?' Possible answers were: (5) 'living really comfortably on present income', (4) 'living comfortably on present income', (3) 'neither comfortable nor struggling on present income', (2) 'struggling on present income', and (1) 'really struggling on present income'. We built a three-category variable: (i) living comfortably on present income (answers 5 and 4), (ii) covering monthly expenses with present income (answer 3), and (iii) having difficulty living on present income (answers 2 and 1).

Considering that the sample was skewed with participants being younger and more educated, we included the following individual demographic and socioeconomic covariates – age, education, marital status, and employment status, which are associated with life satisfaction(10, 110, 158, 159), as well as the appropriate adjustment(185).

The variable of age was treated as continuous to adjust for the skewed younger age. Education level was treated as categorical to adjust for the overrepresentation of more-educated participants, with the following categories: (i) no degree and primary school. (ii) secondary school, and (iii) university.

We additionally included two individual covariates that are commonly associated with potential biases in convenience samples: The employment situation included the following categories: (i) full-time and part-time employed, (ii) unemployed, (iii) student, and (iv) retired/other. This control variable can be related to both age and education and helps control for potential bias. The second covariate was the participants' relationship status, with the following categories: (i) single, (ii) in a relationship, and (iii) I don't know. Participants' relationship status can be related to age and socioeconomic gradient and helps control for potential bias.

Sexual identity was defined with the following question: 'People are different in their sexual attraction to other people. Which best describes your feelings? Are you...' Possible answers included: (i) 'attracted to other men or gay', (ii) 'attracted to other women or lesbian', (iii) 'attracted to both men and women or bisexual', (iv) 'straight or heterosexual', (v) I don't know or questioning. Gender identity was defined with the combination of the following two questions in a single categorical variable: 'What sex were you assigned at birth?' with the following possible answers: (i) 'intersex/ambiguous', (ii) female', (iii) 'male'. The second question was 'How do you define your gender identity? (tick as many as apply).' Possible answers were: (i) man, (ii) trans man (female to male), (iii) trans woman (male to female), (iv) woman, and (v) 'non-binary gender (third gender, Pavaiyaa, Hijra, Kinnar)'. The inclusion of a gender identity categorical variable in a multilevel regression is a straightforward way to account for the overrepresentation of cisgender men and reflect the variability of each gender category, leading to more accurate estimates of the regression's results(185).

Self-declared HIV status was measured with the following question: 'Do you know your HIV status?'. Possible answers were: (i) I'm HIV-negative, (ii) I'm HIV-positive, (iii) I don't know, and (iv) I don't want to answer. The complete questionnaire of the Global LGBT Happiness Survey is available in the Online Supplementary Material.

We also included country-level control variables such as unemployment, inflation, the gross national income in purchasing power parity, and the Gini index(173). These country-level variables were log-transformed to approximate a normal/Gaussian distribution and smooth the relationship with the dependent variable.

Statistical analyses

Multilevel models

We developed a linear multilevel mixed-effect model to analyse the determinants of happiness in the LGBTQ+ participants. An interesting feature of this modelling approach is that it considers the two-level data structure: the fact that individuals (level 1) are nested into countries (level 2), as well as the presence of correlation between individuals from the same country(186). In other words, individuals in the same country share observed and unobserved social and economic characteristics. The decomposition of the unobserved terms, i.e. *i*) the individual one and *ii*) that related to the individuals of the same group, enabled variability both between individuals and between countries. We included a random slope model to account for the potential random effects of level-2 variables on happiness.

Individual-level variables were collected directly from the participants of the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey. These included variables such as sexual and gender identities, the micro and meso levels of homophobic discrimination, economic precarity, education, and self-reported HIV status, as well as the outcome variable: subjective well-being. Country-level measures are contextual variables reflecting countries' characteristics in terms of macroeconomic and social environments. These included variables such as gross domestic product per capita, the Gini index, HIV prevalence, unemployment and inflation rate.

By performing the likelihood ratio test and Akaike information criterion, we confirmed that the multilevel model better fits the data and explained the most significant variation using the fewest

possible independent variables (see SMS9 for more details). All econometric models used the same sample and control variables described in Table 1. Analyses were stratified according to the level of economic precarity to control for economic heterogeneity in the study population and investigate the role of the different variables of homophobia according to the level of precarity. Three multilevel models were performed to investigate the determinants of well-being in each subgroup: (i) participants having difficulty living with their present income, (ii) participants covering monthly expenses with their present income, and (iii) participants living comfortably with their present income. All econometric models used the same sample, whether stratified or not, and included all control variables described in Table 1.

Finally, to investigate in greater detail the differential association of homophobia variables according to the precarity situation, we tested the presence of statistically significant interactions between the measures of economic precarity and each dimension of homophobic stigma and discrimination in the multilevel model on well-being. The regression models with interactions included all the covariates of the main regression model. All statistical analyses were conducted using standard commands available in Stata 17.

Dominance analysis and sensitivity analysis

To assess the weight or importance of each dimension of homophobic stigma and discrimination in the explained variance, we performed a dominance analysis⁽⁸⁴⁾ of the multilevel model⁽¹⁸⁷⁾. The dominance analysis enables the evaluation of the additional contribution of each dimension of stigma and discrimination into the model by analysing the changes in explained variance after introducing each homophobia dimension in the model, considering the control variables⁽⁸⁵⁾. The 95% confidence intervals for the dominance analysis were estimated through acknowledged methods, with the bootstrapping method, with 1,000 replications, providing precise and reliable measures^(188, 189).

We also investigated the linearity of the subjective well-being scale; in other words, whether the numerical rating of this subjective scale was cardinally comparable. To do so, we assessed whether monotonic transformations of the well-being measure could lead to estimation issues^(87-89, 190), applying Schroeder and Yitzhaki's line of independence minus absolute concentration curve as well as Bloem and Oswald's dichotomous around the median tests (see SMS7 for further details).

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author (EL) to all accredited researchers upon request and signature of a declaration of confidentiality and privacy. Please note that due to the existence of national legislation criminalising sexual and gender diverse people, the above declaration requests all data related to the LGBTI Global Survey to be treated following the EU Directive 95/46/EC and as amended, replaced or superseded from time to time, including by the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

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Authors' contributions

EL, SH and BV conceptualised the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey. EL and SH conducted and implemented the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey. EL, BV and SH are exclusively responsible for the survey data used in this study. EL, BV, VL and SB conceptualised the study. EL, BV, VL, SH and SB drafted the manuscript. VL, BV, and EL conducted the data analysis. EL, BV, VL, and SH were primarily responsible for the final content of the manuscript. All authors had full access to all the data in the study. EL, BV, and VL verified the underlying data of the study. All authors approved the final manuscript.

All authors contributed to this article in their personal capacity. The views expressed are their own and do not necessarily represent the views of their respective institutions.

Competing interests

EL and SH declare they work for UNAIDS and the LGBTQ+ Foundation, respectively. Both organisations are engaged in advocacy on HIV and the reduction of societal barriers, including those applied to sexual and gender diverse communities. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

Tables

Level of well-being (a)	n / % (b)	Coefficient (c)	P> z (d)	[95% conf. interval] (e)	
Gender identity					
Non-binary	5,270 (6.4)	-0.179	< 0.001	-0.236	-0.121
Trans feminine	3,230 (3.9)	-0.094	0.015	-0.169	-0.018
Trans masculine	2,042 (2.5)	0.085	0.067	-0.006	0.176
Cisgender men	66,249 (80.5)	(Base)			
Cisgender women	5,533 (6.7)	-0.258	< 0.001	-0.329	-0.186
Sexual orientation					
Gay men	59,614 (72.4)	(Base)			
Lesbian	3,332 (4.0)	0.226	< 0.001	0.139	0.313
Bisexual	14,956 (18.1)	0.127	< 0.001	0.088	0.165
Straight	578 (0.7)	0.075	0.388	-0.095	0.245
Questioning and queer	3,844 (4.7)	0.145	< 0.001	0.077	0.212
Employment					
Full-time employed	51 886 (63)	(Base)			
Part-time	4,998 (6.1)	-0.170	< 0.001	-0.228	-0.112
Unemployed	8,625 (10.5)	-0.482	< 0.001	-0.529	-0.435
Student	13 604 (16.5)	-0.036	0.094	-0.082	0.006
Retired/other	3,211 (3.9)	-0.009	0.820	-0.082	0.065
HIV status					
HIV-Negative	51,344 (63.0)	(Base)			
HIV-Positive	9,024 (11.0)	-0.135	< 0.001	-0.180	-0.090
Do not want to answer	3,386 (4.1)	0.076	0.030	0.007	0.144
Do not know	18,570 (22.6)	-0.198	< 0.001	-0.232	-0.164
Age ^a	2.15 (1.10)	-0.066	0.018	-0.120	-0.011
Age squared ^a	5.85 (6.11)	0.031	< 0.001	0.022	0.041
Education					
Primary/none ^b	2,207 (2.7)	0.396	< 0.001	0.309	0.483
Secondary/high school	21,171 (25.7)	(Base)			
University first degree	44,232 (53.7)	0.073	< 0.001	0.040	0.106
Master/doctorate	14,714 (17.9)	0.126	< 0.001	0.082	0.171
Relationship status					
Single	51,924 (63.1)	(Base)			
In a relationship	28,438 (34.5)	0.505	< 0.001	0.476	0.534
I don't know	1,962 (2.4)	-0.017	0.700	-0.105	0.071
Economic and financial situation					
Having difficulty living on present income	21,628 (26.2)	(Base)			
Covering monthly expenses	32,489 (39.5)	0.759	< 0.001	0.724	0.794

with present income					
Living comfortably on present income	28,207 (34.3)	1.577	< 0.001	1.539	1.614
Homophobic stigma and discrimination (3 dimensions)					
Family homophobia					
Yes	43,631 (53)	-0.837	< 0.001	-0.866	-0.808
No	38,693 (47)	(Base)			
Homophobic reactions: Insulted					
Yes	48,390 (58.8)	-0.243	< 0.001	-0.272	-0.213
No	33,934 (41.2)	(Base)			
Homophobic reactions: Physical					
Yes	17,437 (21.2)	-0.213	< 0.001	-0.248	-0.177
No	64,887 (78.8)	(Base)			
	M (SD)				
Country's homophobic climate	0.58 (0.14)	-1.684	< 0.001	-2.383	-0.986
Inflation ^c	1.49 (0.71)	-0.083	0.032	-0.160	-0.007
Gross national income ^c	9.86 (0.70)	-0.360	< 0.001	-0.477	-0.243
Unemployment	7.21 (4.48)	-0.019	0.015	-0.034	-0.004
Gini ^c	3.65 (0.20)	0.822	< 0.001	0.480	1.163
Constant		7.302	< 0.001	5.221	9.383
N		82 324			
Number of groups (countries)		153			
Var(Residual)		3.766		3.730	3.802

Table 1 | Descriptive statistics and multilevel regression model of the association between well-being and socioeconomic, health, and homophobia-related variables. This table presents two levels of information. First, a description of the variables with their distribution is provided in the second column: the number of participants and their proportion (%) for categorical variables; the mean and standard deviations (SD) for continuous variables. Second, the four columns on the right provide the results of a multilevel linear regression model examining the association between well-being and three dimensions of homophobia: family, community (verbal and physical homophobic reactions), and institutional (HCI). The regression model includes random effects for country-level variables and controls for a set of socioeconomic and health variables. The unit refers to survey participants, with $n = 82,324$. Likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2(6) = 1413.98, p < .001$. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple comparisons. *Note (a):* Age and its squared value (age^2) are included as continuous variables to explore the potential non-linear U-shaped association between age and happiness. Values in the second column for these two continuous variables are the means and standard deviations. In subsequent regressions and tables, we used the linear form of the variable age to improve the convergence properties of the model without altering the coefficients of the clustered regressions. *Note (b):* We aggregated the first categories of Education to have groups of balanced sizes. *Note (c):* Inflation, gross national income and Gini index have been log-transformed to approximate a normal Gaussian distribution and smooth the relationship with the dependent variable.

Level of well-being	Coefficient	P > z	[95% conf. interval]	
Having difficulty living on present income				
Family homophobia	-0.903	< 0.001	-0.968	-0.838
Homophobic reactions: Insulted	-0.266	< 0.001	-0.337	-0.196
Homophobic reactions: Physical	-0.321	< 0.001	-0.392	-0.250
Country's homophobic climate	-2.294	< 0.001	-3.261	-1.327
Constant	7.318	< 0.001	4.341	10.29
n	21,628			
Number of groups (countries)	147			
Covering monthly expenses on present income				
Family homophobia	-0.811	< 0.001	-0.855	-0.768
Homophobic reactions: Insulted	-0.178	< 0.001	-0.223	-0.134
Homophobic reactions: Physical	-0.172	< 0.001	-0.225	-0.118
Country's homophobic climate	-1.780	< 0.001	-2.577	-0.982
Constant	7.008	< 0.001	4.34103	10.29443
n	32,489			
Number of groups (countries)	149			
Living comfortably on present income				
Family homophobia	-0.793	< 0.001	-0.840	-0.746
Homophobic reactions: Insulted	-0.305	< 0.001	-0.352	-0.259
Homophobic reactions: Physical	-0.119	< 0.001	-0.181	-0.057
Country's homophobic climate	-1.174	0.001	-1.876	-0.472
Constant	8.061	< 0.001	5.942	10.18
n	28,207			
Number of groups (countries)	150			

Table 2 | The Association Between Well-being and the Three Dimensions of Homophobia, Clustered by Income Level. The table presents the coefficients from three multilevel linear regression models of well-being stratified by income levels (in bold) (having difficulty living on present income, covering monthly expenses with present income, and living comfortably on present income). The regression models included all the control variables presented in Table 1. Detailed regression results are presented in S.M5. The unit refers to survey participants, with $n=82,324$ in the full sample. Subsample numbers per income level (n) are presented in the table. Likelihood ratio tests: $\chi^2(6)=502.06, p<.001$; $\chi^2(6)=553.36, p<.001$; $\chi^2(6)=239.33, p<.001$.

Level of well-being	Coefficient	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Measures:				
Family homophobia	-0.930	< 0.001	-0.985	-0.874
Homophobic reactions: Insulted	-0.272	< 0.001	-0.333	-0.211
Homophobic reactions: Physical	-0.322	< 0.001	-0.384	-0.260
Country's Homophobic Climate Index (HCI)	-2.270	0.001	-3.015	-1.527
Interactions:				
Income: Covering monthly expenses* x Family homophobia	0.124	0.001	0.052	0.195
Income: Living comfortably** x Family homophobia	0.149	< 0.001	0.075	0.224
Income: Covering monthly expenses* x Insulted	0.093	0.017	0.017	0.170
Income: Living comfortably** x Insulted	-0.028	0.487	-0.106	0.050
Income: Covering monthly expenses* x Physical	0.148	0.001	0.064	0.231
Income: Living comfortably** x Physical	0.200	< 0.001	0.110	0.290
Income: Covering monthly expenses* x HCI	0.490	0.018	0.083	0.972
Income: Living comfortably** x HCI	1.057	< 0.001	0.642	1.471
n	82,324			
Number of groups (countries)	153			

Table 3 | Association between well-being and the three dimensions of homophobia, including interactions with economic security. Multilevel linear regression models of well-being and the three dimensions of homophobia. The models include interactions between the various dimensions of homophobia and the levels of economic security (covering monthly expenses with present income* and living comfortably on present income**). Those having difficulty living on their present income are the reference group. The regression models were performed with the same control variables as in Table 1. The unit of analysis is the survey participant, with $n=82,324$ in the full sample. Likelihood ratio tests: $\chi^2(6)=1410.35, p<.001$. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple comparisons.

Level of economic security	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
	Low* (95% CI)	Middle** (95% CI)	Higher*** (95% CI)	Average (95% CI)
Family homophobia (%)	16.1 (12.4, 19.8)	13.3 (9.7, 16.9)	7.8 (5.3, 10.2)	12.4 (10.5, 14.3)
Share of family homophobia in the dominance of the three dimensions of homophobia taken together (%)	44.1	39.7	58.6	47.5
Homophobic reactions (%)	9.8 (6.7, 12.9)	5.9 (3.0, 8.7)	2.8 (1.3, 4.2)	6.2 (4.7, 7.6)
Share of homophobic reactions (verbal and physical) in the dominance of the three dimensions of homophobia taken together (%)	26.8	17.6	21.1	21.8
Country's homophobic climate (%)	10.6 (6.4, 14.7)	14.3 (8.5, 20.1)	2.7 (1.0, 4.7)	9.2 (6.8, 11.6)
Share of the homophobic climate index in the dominance of the three dimensions of homophobia taken together (%)	29.0	42.7	20.3	30.7
Dominance statistics of the three dimensions of homophobia (%)	36.5 100	33.5 100	13.3 100	27.8 100
n	21,628	32,489	28,207	82,324

Table 4 | Relative importance of the three dimensions of homophobia on well-being, clustered by level of economic security. The table presents the percentages of explained variance in well-being by the three dimensions of homophobia (in bold): family, community, and country, stratified by level of economic security: having difficulty living on present income*, covering monthly expenses with present income**, and living comfortably on present income***. Dominance analysis was used to determine the relative importance of each dimension and was performed with the same control variables as in Table 1. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple comparisons. The 95% confidence intervals for dominance analysis in columns (a) to (d) were estimated through bootstrapping method, with 1,000 replications (188, 189). The unit of analysis is the survey participant, with $n=82,324$ in the full sample. The number of participants per income level (n) subsamples are presented at the bottom of the table. Likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2(6)=1413.98, p < .001$.

Figure legends/captions

Fig. 1 | Distribution of the LGBTQ+ Happiness Index Worldwide. The index is divided into three categories and distributed across six distinct regions. The categories correspond to thresholds for the 11-item Cantril ladder of life satisfaction: *suffering* refers to participants who responded from 0 to 4 on the life satisfaction happiness scale; *struggling* refers to responses of 5 or 6; *thriving* refers to responses from 7 to 10. The unit refers to survey participants, with $n=82,324$. Values are authors' calculations using the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey. Welch's ANOVA: $F(5,82,318)=575.12, p < .001$, effect size (η^2) = 0.034. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple comparisons.

Fig. 2 | Distribution of individual-level homophobic measures worldwide. The figure illustrates two socioecological dimensions of homophobia across the regions, the family and the community ones. The family dimension is measured with the proportions of participants facing homophobia at the family level. The community dimension has two measures: having been verbally insulted and having been physically assaulted. Values are based on the authors' calculations using primary data from the Global LGBTQ+ Happiness Survey. The unit refers to survey participants, with $n=82,324$. $\chi^2(5)=3.3 e^3, p < .001$; $\chi^2(5)=1.4 e^3, p < .001$; $\chi^2(5)=4.1 e^3, p < .001$. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple.

Fig. 3 | Homophobia and well-being: strength of the association by sexual identity and by region. The figure presents eight forest plots showing the correlation between well-being and the various measures of homophobia, stratified by sexual orientation and region. The beta coefficient is the measure of central tendency, represented by a dot, and the whiskers indicate the 95% confidence interval for each stratification. **Fig. 3a** presents the stratification per sexual identity. **Fig. 3b** presents the stratification per region. The regression models were performed with the same control variables as in Table 1. The sample size refers to survey participants. The number of participants per sexual identity (Fig. 3a) was $n=81,746$. This does not include 578 transgender participants who reported their sexual identity as 'straight' and therefore do not appear here. The number of participants per region (Fig. 3b) was $n=82,324$. Subsample sizes are available in SM S4. Likelihood ratio tests, ordered following the variables in the keys are: $\chi^2(6)=1413.98, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=992.92, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=40.52, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=194.81, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=27.41, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=68.32, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=0.00, p = 1$; $\chi^2(6)=1.23, p = 0.9752$; $\chi^2(6)=39.83, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=107.49, p < .001$; $\chi^2(6)=30.99, p < .001$. All statistical tests were two-sided. No adjustments were made for multiple comparisons.

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